

**Sustainable Retail Transformation through Visual Merchandising:
Examining the Mediating Impact of Brand and Store Image on
Consumer Purchase Intention**

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Abstract

The visual merchandising, environment of the retail industry has the significance dynamic and provides the competitive advantages, thus the displaying the products and brands has greater impact on the buying behavior of the consumers in the sector of retail super stores, which is recognized as the field of visual merchandising and as well as store design. Actually, the visual merchandising has the significance importance in the field of marketing and has effective marketing tactics for retailers to increase consumer purchase intention. Therefore, the current research study was examining the visual merchandising effects on the consumer buying behavior with mediating effects of store image and the brand image with the consumer purchase intention. Thus, the research study was used the approach of primary data to analysis the consumer buying behavior in the field of visual merchandising, through the administrative questionnaire, the non-probability convenience sampling techniques to collect the data from the retail visual merchandising stores in the city of Karachi. Through the results of the path coefficients, showing the direct relationship, the independent variables of the visual merchandising with the dependent variable store image and brand image. The findings suggested that the all the hypotheses of the visual merchandising statistically and the positively associated with the dependent variables of store image and brand image. The mediating effects of the relationship and the hypothesis of, Store Image, and brand image mediates the relationship between the window display and the consumer purchase intention, is supported due to the probability value is less than 0.05. Further results indicates that the relationship of the store image mediates the relationship of the store layout and the consumer purchase intention. Through the results, suggested that the store image mediates the

relationship of the color lighting and the consumer purchase intention. Thus, the results indicates that the store image mediates the relationship of the factor of store interior design and the consumer purchase intention. Through the results, suggested that the store image supported the mediating effects of the relationship of the promotional signage and the consumer purchase intention. The results indicates that the store image mediates the relationship of the visual merchandising factor of mannequin display and the consumer purchase intention.

Keywords: Window Display, Color Lighting, Mannequin Display, Store Image, Brand Image, Consumer Purchase Intention

Overview of the Research Study

In the competitive environment, the field of visual merchandising explained as the interior and the exterior design of the stores with products to developed positive consumer attitude, to attract more attentions to increase consumer purchase intention (Ali et al., 2023). The prior research study was suggested that the visual merchandising is the include of the window display, the forum display and the includes the promotion signage with floor merchandising, because the displaying goods more attractive for consumer and creates more attentions. The technique of the visual merchandising has the significance regarding the brands visually making for the purpose to attract customers and displaying with highlights differentiate characteristics and features in the shopping malls and as well as stores to enhance customer purchase intention (Jeong & Kim, 2022). The prior research study was suggested that in the retail super stores, the visual attractions and with the better communications always have significance importance and thus, visual merchandising has the important marketing tactics in the retail sector and as well as retail shopping malls. For the purpose to increase consumer purchase intentions and increase market shares in the competitive environments, more focus on the visual merchandising strategies and the techniques in the retailing operations (Mondol et al., 2021). Thus, in the success of the retail store business, the visual merchandising is one of the benefiting techniques and strategies and attractive for customers, through the both interior and the exterior features and also positive impact on the consumer purchase intention (Ali, Nasir, & Haider, 2025). Through this approach the retailer has better understanding about consumer needs and better decisions regarding the right products for the right customers (Ali et al., 2017). The prior research study was suggested that the effects of visual merchandising regarding the psychological consumer behavior through the visually communications and trying the better communicate regarding the messages through the utilized the visual merchandising and create positive attitude, if the marketing expert not successful to delivered messages, then create negative consumer attitude towards brands, shopping malls, retail outlets (Sari & Turhan, 2022). To enhance the consumer purchase intention in the visual merchandising, the significance selection such as the right color, effects of the lighting, products on the shelving and store layout, window display (Wijaya & Sander, 2018). Actually, these factors have been significance important considered to increase revenues in the retail

outlets and shopping malls and to increase consumer purchase intention through the visually display products also differentiate the brands, thus, to create positive attitude (Wang et al., 2022). The field of visual merchandising has a significance importance in the competitive business, and effective marketing strategies improve the firm performance and generate the profitability. Therefore, all set of activities, or marketing strategies is the way of methods to transferring finished goods from the manufactured to the end consumers sale of point, or the place of the convenience stores to easily access consumer products (Ali, Iqbal, Boumal, & Raza, 2025). The prior research study suggested that, the visual merchandising is the part of the marketing, and the marketing is the oldest concept on the world and human history support the marketing approaches in the business, in the sales, in the promotions, advertising, branding and visual merchandising (Karunaratne, 2021). Thus, the main objectives of the current research study were investigating the visual merchandising effects on the consumer purchase intention with the mediating effects of brand image, store image and consumer attitude and the moderating effects of brand loyalty, the all these constructs to know the better understanding consumer buying behavior. The research study aims to explored the concept of the visual merchandising factors on the behavior of the consumer with the mediating effects of store image, brand image, consumer attitudes and the moderating effects of the brand loyalty of the different shopping malls in the city of Karachi, to increase consumer purchase intention and to improve better decision making to developed visual merchandising, marketing strategies and more attract to new customers in the context of Pakistan environments. The research study includes the important feature of the visual merchandising and the developed the research hypotheses which are related to the elements of the visual merchandising, store layout, window display, color and lighting and the store interior, with mediating effects, store image, brand image, consumer attitudes and the moderating effects of brand loyalty and how these constructs effects on the consumers attentions.

The Propose Research Study

The research study was examining and investigates the Mediating Impact of Brand and Store Image on the Link Between Visual Merchandising and the Consumer Purchase Intention. Thus, the external factors were examining the visual merchandising and the factors of the visual merchandising are the analysis in the different retail sectors, such as fashion brands, thus the current research study more focus on the visual merchandising elements which are associated with the behavior of the consumers and the elements are Window display, Color Lighting, Mannequin Display, Store Image, Brand Image associated with consumer buying behavior

Problem Statement of the Study

The research study was examining the effects of the marketing approach in the sector of retail shopping environments, and the Mediating Impact of Brand and Store Image on the Link Between Visual Merchandising and the Consumer Purchase Intention, for the purpose of the better understanding of the consumer behavior (Huang, 2024).

Thus, the investigates the relationships of the exogenous variable visual merchandising and the endogenous variable consumer purchase intention, with the mediating role of the brand image and the store image, with associated the behavior of the consumers. Therefore, the main objective of the current research study to examines and integrated theoretical information on the based on the visual merchandising and with relate the information regarding the mediating effects of brand image and the store image and consumer purchase intention, and the factors of the visual merchandising in the competitive business environment, and draw the conclusion. Thus, the study was suggested that in the visual merchandising competitive business environments, the factors of the visual merchandising elements considered more important to better business growth, and further examines and also brand and the store image has more important to better and associated with consumer buying behavior and developed the better development relationship with the consumers

The Research Questions

The current research study has the different research questions:

RQ-1: What are the effects of the window display on the store image?

RQ-2: What are the effects of the window display on the brand image?

RQ-3: What is the impact of the color lighting on the store image?

RQ-4: What is the impact of the color lighting on the brand image?

RQ-5: What is the impact of the mannequin display on the store image?

RQ-6: What is the impact of the mannequin display on the brand image?

RQ-7: What is the impact of the mannequin display on the brand image?

RQ-8: What are the mediating effects of store image and the store image between the independent and the dependent variable?

Research Objectives

The research study objective to explore the concept of the visual merchandising effects on the consumer purchase intention and focus on, how has the significance importance on the store image, with the consumer purchase intention.

RO-1: To examines the effects of the window display on the store image

RO-2: To investigates the effects of the window display on the brand image

RO-3: To analysis the impact of the color lighting on the store image

RO-4: To examines the impact of the color lighting on the brand image

RO-5: To examines the impact of the mannequin display on the store image

RO-6: To investigates s the impact of the mannequin display on the brand image

RO-7: To examines the impact of the mannequin display on the brand image

RO-8: To investigates the mediating effects of store image and the store image between the I independent and the dependent variable

The Limitations of the Research Study

The research study was investigating “The Mediating Impact of Brand and Store Image on the Link Between Visual Merchandising and the Consumer Purchase

Intention”, and with during research study have some limitations founds. The data collected from the respondent, the city of Karachi, and the data was based on the geographically limitations of the boundaries of the research study, because when data collected from the different cities of the Pakistan, then different results, and different perceptions regarding the factors visual merchandising, such as the window display, color lighting, mannequin, display mediating effects of brand image and the store image with the consumer behavior. Also, the current research study was based on the approach of the quantitative research methods, and the data collected through the survey forms, visits big shopping malls in the city of Karachi, but could be different results, if data collected through the approach of the qualitative research methods.

The Scope of the Research Study

The research study primarily examines the factors of the visual merchandising in the shopping malls, such as Dolman Mall Clifton, Port Grand, Dolman Mall Tariq Road, Lucky One Mall, Park Towers, Atrium Mall, Emerald Tower, Dolman Mall Hyderi, Millennium Mall, in the city of Karachi. Because the city of Karachi living all types of the cultural peoples, and societies. All these peoples have visits in these shopping malls, and have greater shopping experiences, the author collect data from the respondent, living in the city of Karachi. Many research study focusses on the visual merchandising impact on the consumer purchase intention, the current research study also includes the more factors of the visual merchandising and examines the mediating effects of the store image, brand image, and consumer attitude and the moderating role of the brand loyalty with the consumer purchase intention.

Thematic Scope of the Study

Basically, the research study was significance and the examines the relationships of the factors associated with the visual merchandising in form of comprehensive regarding the retail's outlets in the shopping malls, associated with the impact on the consumer purchase intention. The research study developed the conceptual research model, which is integrated mediating constructs, store image, with the consumer purchase intention.

Geographic Scope of the Study

The current research study was investigating the retails outlets of the major shopping centers in the city of Karachi, with examines the impact of the visual merchandising on the consumer purchase intention, integrated the mediating effects of the store image, brand image, and consumer attitude and the moderating effects of brand loyalty. The research study aims to explored the concept of the visual merchandising factors on the behavior of the consumer with the mediating effects of store image, brand image, consumer attitudes and the moderating effects of the brand loyalty of the different shopping malls in the city of Karachi, to increase consumer purchase intention and to improve better decision making to developed visual merchandising, marketing strategies and more attract to new customers in the context of Pakistan environments. The research study includes the important feature of the visual

merchandising and the developed the research hypotheses which are related to the elements of the visual merchandising, store layout, window display, color and lighting and the store interior, with mediating effects, store image, brand image, consumer attitudes and the moderating effects of brand loyalty and how these constructs effects on the consumers attentions.

Visual Merchandising and Consumer Purchase Intention

Prior research explained that in the visual merchandising the window display, show window, trade magazine developed significance importance for retail merchandiser. Because the retails super stores, or brand outlets use as the strong tool, approach to better connects customers and more attracts customer when during visits outlets (Ali, Nasir, & Haider, 2025). Thus, the visual merchandiser experts, design outlets in form of lighting, roofs colors, promotions activities, layout, shelf arrangements, window display, these factors positive impact on the potential customer (Asirvatham, & Mohan, 2019). When entered the fashion stores, clothing stores, and jewelry stores have different attitudes and have different consumer behaviors and developed images, and messages. Each message is important for visual merchandising retailer, because each message have effects with the consumer attitudes (Lee et al., 2023)

Brand Image and Visual Merchandising

The two important elements of the brand equity, are brand image and brand awareness, and the brand image associated with the visual merchandising (Keller,1993). Because the brand is referred as sign, name, symbol, or the compensations of these, to differentiated the brands as compare to competitors to increase consumer purchase intention (Kotler and Keller, 2012). The current research study literature based on the visual merchandising factors, brand image, store image, consumer attitudes and what factors are important to presentations for customer in the retail outlets in the shopping malls, how to developed in the mind of customer the brand image, with differentiations, with unique characteristics, and the creates customers beliefs regarding the brands, and to see what perceive customer brand image during visits brand outlets in the shopping malls in the field of visual merchandising (Annas, & Pramudito, 2021). Many past research studies suggested that the visual merchanting is the strong tool, to use to attracts the customer, developed the brand image, interest of the customer, enhanced the store environments in the mind of the customers, with the factor of the visual merchandising, color, lighting, texture, to creates connections with customers, shopping atmosphere, and enjoying shopping and increase consumer purchase intention (Amelindha Vania, 2021). Thus, the activities of the visual merchandising, the developed the strong associations with the customers selections of the brands, through the display of the window, floor merchandising, through signage, the point of sale all these factors impact on the brand image and the consumer purchase intention (Asirvatham, & Mohan, 2019)

Store Image and Visual Merchandising

The customers choosing the brand outlets, or shopping malls, based on the store image, and as well as visual merchandising, impact on customer shopping malls choices. Thus, the store image has the positively and the significantly associated with the visual merchandises and the consumer purchase intention. Actually, the successful shopping selection relates to the different factors of the visual merchandising and the competitive business environments (Kyounggha & Young-Sun Rhee, 2017). Through the past research study, explained that the store image has the significantly and the positively associated with the consumer purchase intention and importance play in the visual merchandising (Ali, Khan, Iqbal, Bukhari, & Boumal, 2025). Thus, the during the shopping in the shopping mall, the store image describe the personality of the store image and this way the store image has the represents the positive image and the good experience and developed positive and tangible store benefits and developed positive image on the consumer purchase intention (Mansouri Moayed et al., 2017). Therefore, the qualities of the store image, the store image characteristics, layout of the store, location, light impacts, described the differentiations and these factors associated with visual merchandising and positive impact on the consumer purchase intention (Wijaya, & Sander, 2018). Thus, customer has the developed the positive perceptions based on the factors of the tangible and the intangible and creates the store image identity and influence on the consumer purchase intention (Gupta, & Coskun, 2021).

Consumer Attitudes and Visual Merchandising

During the shopping mall, and the visual merchandising has the positive attitude based on the store image, brand image and the factors of the visual merchandising, such as the factors, interior design, exterior design, color, lighting and display window associated with the consumer attitude and impact on the behavior of the consumer purchase intention (Kyounggha & Young-Sun Rhee, 2017). The association of the visual merchandising associated with consumer perceptions and thus, developed relationship positively with the behavior of the consumers, and the visual merchandising is based on the branded retail store display of the merchandising, to connect with the customers, and more attracts potential customers and encourage the more customers to enter the outlets, and create positive store image, and significance impact on the consumer attitude (Ali, Siddiqui, Ali, & Lutfullah, 2025)

Theoretical Framework & Background

Because the good presentation of any brand the window of the store significance importance and make the strong visual communication tool to attract consumers and to create opportunities for target audience to enter stores. In the city of Karachi, there are many shopping stores and shopping mall, such as ocean mall Clifton, Millenium mall, Dolman mall, lucky One mall, Atrium mall, more focus on the visual merchandising to increase consumer purchase intention. Different elements of the visual merchandising are exterior store design, layout store, interior store design, display store interior. Impact on the behavior on the consumer buying behavior.

Actually, in the retail outlets, the store of the window display is the good approach of the presentation of the brand, thus the communication of the visual which significance and probability to attract target audience to enter the shopping malls, such as big shopping malls, used these marketing approach to create store image, brand image, and developed consumer attitude to enhance consumer purchase intention (Lea-Greenwood, 2012).

The Conceptual Research Model, the Consumer Purchase Intention: Figure: 2.1

Development Research Hypotheses

H1: Window display has the significantly and the positively associated with Store Image

H2: Color lighting has the significantly and the positively associated with Store Image

H3: Mannequin display has the significantly and the positively associated with Store Image

H4: Window display has the significantly and the positively associated with Brand Image

H5: Color lighting has the significantly and the positively associated with Brand Image

H6: Mannequin display has the significantly and the positively associated with Brand Image

H7: Store Image mediates the relationship between the window display and the consumer purchase intention

H8: Store Image mediates the relationship between the color lighting and the consumer purchase intention

H9: Store Image mediates the relationship between the Mannequin display and the consumer purchase intention

H10: Brand Image mediates the relationship between the window display and the consumer purchase intention

H11: Brand Image mediates the relationship between the color lighting and the consumer purchase intention

H12: Brand Image mediates the relationship between the Mannequin display and the consumer purchase intention

H13: Store Image has the significance impact on the consumer purchase intention

H14: Brand Image has the significance impact on the consumer purchase intention

Research Design

The research design is the way of collection data, for the purpose to confirm specific theories and the data analysis through the statistical technique, the current research study is the quantitative research approach which based on the close ended questionnaire. Thus, the main objective of the current research study was to examines the relationships visual merchandising effects with the mediating effects of consumer attitudes and the dependent variable of consumer purchase intention, also the moderating role of store image. The current research design based on the cross sectional descriptive and the causal research designs, explanatory with mixed approach of the research. The structured questionnaire has used to gather the data. Because the quantitative research design applies for the objective of quantitative data analysis to test the research hypothesis. Therefore, the most advantages of the considered the quantitative analysis is that this approach provides the significance results in term of quantifying the data could be easy to validate in the research study. The current research based on the quantitative approach, and the type of research is causal descriptive research, to analysis the descriptive phenomenon and causes regarding the endogenous and the exogenous variables to be studies. Thus, the data collect through the distributed questionnaire, to experts the knowledge, the subject of the human resource, and the students the field of human resource, and have the experience at any organizations.

Research Approach

The research approach is based on the procedure and the plans to analysis the research, to collection data, results interpretations, and the approach of quantitative research approach was used the current research study. The current research study examines the different factors of the visual merchandising on the retail stores with the consumer purchase intention, the data collect from the respondent, those have the experiences of the retail shopping stores and based on the quantitative research methods to developed the hypotheses and the empirically verified the hypotheses of the current research study. Thus, the researchers have combined quantitative and qualitative research approaches, inductive and deductive investigation approaches,

study purposes (contextual analysis, experimental investigation), and research methods (survey, questionnaire, and experiment) to establish a relationship between these expressions.

Target Population, Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Through the non-probability, the convenience sampling technique to collected data, and the size of the sample to be 350, the respondents from the fashion super stores in the city of Karachi. The research study used the primary data and the data is the relevant to the research study and all data of the sample for this study will consist of finance and the experts of the financial markets, and knowing the experience any organizations or has the knowledge of human resource management. A convenience sampling technique will be employed to select participants who meet the inclusion criteria. The sample size, 350 includes with the help of the questionnaire, to collect data, will be determined based on the principle of achieving sufficient statistical power for the analysis. The approach of the data collection through the non-probability sampling, the convenience sampling, has the characteristics based on the cheap and the easy to collect the data, and the respondent, the intended the audience has the specified practical knowledge and the requirement, with accessibility (Bell et al., 2022)

Data Source

The data collection in the current research study includes the primary and the secondary data, the primary data is based on the first-hand data collection, such as data collection through the questionnaire, interview and the focus group, whereas the secondary data was the published data, which is include in the literature. The researcher first built the confidence with respondent that this study is only used for academic purpose not for commercial. The researcher physically attends the respondent to fulfill the questionnaire from selected the human resource firms. The researcher asked for permission from the manager or with other heads and build their trust that their opinions are confidential so that they give information without any hesitation. Give Respondents time to easily fill the questionnaire because they have their other responsibilities so gave them free hand for the questionnaire. This makes the answer more reliable because respondents filled the questionnaire without any pressure and they gave you other primary information which will be helpful for the research. Each questionnaire filled 10 to 15 minutes so that each question get time and answered correctly. Questionnaire is personally filled by the respondents for primary data collection. Actually, the current research study was based on the primary data approach, to examines the research study developed the hypothesis, and the data collection in the study the first time specific and significance objectives.

Data Analysis Techniques

Through the Smart PLS 3.0 to use the data analysis and the compatibility with the chosen analytical techniques and the researchers' familiarity with the software By employing a rigorous research design, collecting relevant data, and utilizing

appropriate analysis techniques, this study aims to provide valuable insights into the impact of visual merchandising elements of retail stores on consumer purchase intention. analysis the mediating effects of store image. The next chapter will present the data analysis and findings derived from the collected data.

Table Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha for Internal Consistency

Constructs	Cronbach's alpha>0.7	Composite reliability (rho_a)>0.7	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Brand Image	0.834	0.850	0.890	0.671
Color & Lighting	0.842	0.841	0.906	0.762
Consumer Purchase Intention	0.832	0.837	0.887	0.663
Mannequin display	0.774	0.780	0.868	0.687
Store Image	0.840	0.840	0.904	0.759
Window Display	0.771	0.798	0.853	0.593
Brand Image	0.834	0.850	0.890	0.671

The prior research study was suggested that, in the PLS-SEM, examines, the measurement of the construct reliability with the help of the results of the or through the internal consistency methods, the constructs of the study (Straub et al., 2004). Thus, the internal consistency analysis through the values of the Cronbach Alpha and the Composite reliability (Hair et al., 2012) The results indicates that of Cronbach Alph and the Composite reliability, greater than 0.7, then reached to internal consistency, thus, the research study confirmed the internal consistency. The analysis of the test of the reliability, the explained the internal consistency of the items of the constructs in the research study Thus, the reliability suggested that the characteristics of the reliability and the validity of the items, of the constructs in the research study. The results of the Cronbach's alpha, greater than 0.7, thus concludes that all the construct in the research study valid. All of the results indicate the composite reliability of color lighting=0.928 and the average variance extracted is 0.722, the composite reliability of consumer purchase intention=0.861 and the average extracted =0.610, the results of the Mannequin display =0.644, and the Window display=0.865 and the average variance= 0.616 the results indicate good internal consistency.

Convergent Validity Analysis

The prior research study was explained the convergent validity is the extent to which the items represent as the construct., thus in the partial least square, the convergent validity is analysis and measured the results or values of the average variance extracted must greater than 0.5 (Urbach & Ahlemann, 2010). Thus, the all the items in the constructs more than 0.5, then all the items of the constructs in the research study, the confirmed the existence of the convergent validity. In the study, the data analysis through the factor loading to access the results of the convergent validity of the items, and the average variance extracted and also includes the composite reliability to access the results and verified the data validity. Because the convergent validity is based on the measurement model and examines the variances, includes the AVE and the composite reliability. Thus, the value of the average variance extracted more than 0.5, to validates the results. Therefore, the values of the composite reliability greater then 0.7, the level to confirmatory and if the values greater than 0.8, will be good considered

Discriminant Validity

The prior research study was explained the concept of the discriminant validity; to explain the measured the discriminant validity, each construct is differentiated from the others constructs. Thus, in the partial least square, the discriminant validity is measured, with the help of the results of the cross loading of the items (Henseler et al., 2015). The results indicates that values of the all the constructs explained the discriminant validity, and the discriminant validity is the differentiate from one construct to another construct. Thus, the discriminant validity evaluates the values of the cross-loading, and the square root of the value of Ave=0.722, is 0.850, greater, thus, the construct is differed from the other construct. The Fronell-Larcker criterion is one of the most popular techniques used to check the discriminant validity of measurements models. According to this criterion, the square root of the average variance extracted by a construct must be greater than the correlation between the construct and any other construct.

Fornell-Larcker criterion

Constructs	Brand Image	Color & Lighting	Consumer Purchase Intention	Mannequin display	Store Image	Window Display
Brand Image	0.819					
Color & Lighting	0.681	0.873				
Consumer Purchase Intention	0.776	0.948	0.814			
Mannequin display	0.684	0.530	0.545	0.829		

Store Image	0.792	0.798	0.858	0.570	0.871
Window Display	0.856	0.694	0.755	0.759	0.770

The results indicates that values of the all the constructs explained the discriminant validity, and the discriminant validity is the differentiate from one construct to another construct. Thus, the discriminant validity evaluates the values of the cross-loading, and the square root of the value of Ave=0.722, is 0.850, greater, thus, the construct is differed from the other construct. The Fronell-Larcker criterion is one of the most popular techniques used to check the discriminant validity of measurements models. According to this criterion, the square root of the average variance extracted by a construct must be greater than the correlation between the construct and any other construct.

Figure: Measurement Model

Path Coefficients

Hypothesis	Relationship	P-Value	Results
H1: Window display has the significantly and the positively associated with Store Image	Window Display -> Store Image	0.000	Accepted
H2: Color lighting has the significantly and the positively associated with Store Image	Color & Lighting -> Store Image	0.000	Accepted
H3: Mannequin display has the significantly and the positively associated with Store Image	Mannequin display -> Store Image	0.231	Not Accepted
H4: Window display has the significantly and the positively associated with Brand Image	Window Display -> Brand Image	0.000	Accepted
H5: Color lighting has the significantly and the positively associated with Brand Image	Color & Lighting -> Brand Image	0.001	Accepted
H6: Mannequin display has the significantly and the positively associated with Brand Image	Mannequin display -> Brand Image	0.150	Not Accepted
H13: Store Image has the significance impact on the consumer purchase intention	Store Image -> Consumer Purchase Intention	0.000	Accepted
H14: Brand Image	Brand Image ->	0.000	Accepted

has the significance Consumer Purchase
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 intention

Through the results of the path coefficients, showing the direct relationship, the independent variables of the visual merchandising with the dependent variable store image. The findings suggested that the all the hypotheses of the visual merchandising statistically and the positively associated with the dependent variables of store image. Thus, all the factors of the visual merchandising have the positively associated with the store image. Results suggested that, in the retail sector, the factor of visual merchandising, the window display has the greater impact on the store image, means that window display positive association with the store image. Further the color lighting more significance associated with the store image, thus, concludes that color lighting for customer has the more importance to increased sales and as well as store image. But the results suggested that the mannequin display not positive impact on the store image, because of the probability values greater than 0.05, 0.231.

The results suggested that the window display has the positive association with the brand image, thus concludes that window display of any brand has the greater impact on the brand image, and the color lighting has the positive association with the brand image, but the mannequin display has not associated with the brand image and the store image and the brand image has the positive impact on the consumer purchase intention.

Mediating Effects Results Analysis

Hypothesis	Relationship	P-Value	Results
H7: Store Image mediates the relationship between the window display and the consumer purchase intention	Window Display -> Store Image -> Consumer Purchase Intention	0.000	Accepted
H8: Store Image mediates the relationship between the color lighting and the consumer purchase intention	Color & Lighting -> Store Image -> Consumer Purchase Intention	0.000	Accepted
H9: Store Image	Mannequin display	0.236	

mediates the relationship between Mannequin display and the consumer purchase intention	-> Store Image -> Consumer Purchase Intention		Not Accepted
H10: Brand Image mediates the relationship between window display and the consumer purchase intention	Window Display -> Brand Image -> Consumer Purchase Intention	0.000	Accepted
H11: Brand Image mediates the relationship between the color lighting and the consumer purchase intention	Color & Lighting -> Brand Image -> Consumer Purchase Intention	0.035	Accepted
H12: Brand Image mediates the relationship between Mannequin display and the consumer purchase intention	-> Brand Image -> Consumer Purchase Intention	0.223	Not Accepted

The results suggested that the store image, mediates the relationship between the window display, color lighting, with the consumer purchase intention, and the mannequin display has not mediated with the store image. Further results suggested that the brand image mediates the relationship window display, color lighting, with consumer purchase intention, but not mediates with the mannequin display.

Figure: Structural Model
 Table R-Square

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Brand Image	0.750	0.748
Consumer Purchase Intention	0.761	0.759
Store Image	0.742	0.740

Through the results of the R-Square value=0.761, which is explained the Consumer Purchase Intention, dependent variable explained 76% due to independent variables of the

Brand image and store image. Further results indicate the R-Square=0.750, which is explained variation in the dependent variable, the brand image 75% due to the independent variables in the study, and the store image 74% variation due to the independent variable.

Conclusion

The field of the visual merchandising has the significance importance, and has the competitive advantages in the fashion industry. The visual merchandising, environment of the retail industry has the significance dynamic and provides the competitive advantages, thus the displaying the products and brands has greater impact on the buying behavior of the consumers, which is recognized as the field of visual merchandising and as well as store design. The results indicate the window display, store layout, color lighting, store interior design, promotional signage, mannequin display has the statistically and the positively associated with the consumer purchase intention, thus, concludes that the independent variables have the positive impact on the consumer purchase intention. Actually, the visual merchandising has the significance importance in the field of marketing and has effective marketing tactics for retailers to increase consumer purchase intention. Therefore, the current research study was examining the visual merchandising effects on the consumer buying behavior with mediating effects of store image, brand image and consumer attitudes and the moderating role of brand loyalty to consumer purchase intention. Thus, the research study was used the approach of primary data to analysis the consumer behavior in the field of visual merchandising, through the administrative questionnaire. Through the results of the R-Squar value=0.761, which is explained the Consumer Purchase Intention, dependent variable explained 76%% due to independent variables of the Brand image and store image. Further results indicate the R-Square=0.750, which is explained variation in the dependent variable, the brand image 75% due to the independent variables in the study, and the store image 74% variation duet to the independent variable. Further, results indicate the independent variables, window display, , color lighting, positive impact but the mannequin display not supported

Managerial Contribution

Based on the results, the research study includes the contribution of the managerial, in the industry of the visual merchandising has the significance, and developed the managerial, and strategic strategies to increase consumer purchase intention. The results indicates that the factors of the visual merchandising, such as window display, color lighting, , mannequin display have the significance importance in the mind of the consumer purchase intention. Thus, the retails managers have more invested in these factors to increase consumer purchase intention. Specially the enhanced the friendly environments, for customers and as well as employee. Thus, the current research study effectively in the field of visual merchandising to better understanding of the consumer purchase intention. Based on the results, the developed better pricing strategies, brand development, promotional strategies and to increase consumer purchase intention.

Limitations and Future Research

The current research study has some limitations, and suggested the future directions in the field of visual merchandising, the respondent select from the city of Karachi,

further cities of the Pakistan could be including. The current research study investigates the factors of the visual merchandising, such as the as window display, store layout, color lighting, store interior design, promotional signage, mannequin display has the significance importance in the mind of the consumer purchase intention, more factors could be incorporated in the research model. The current research study examines the mediating effects of the store image, whereas the moderating variables could be incorporated in the research model.

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